

The impact of Covid-19 on the tourism sector in Morocco: Using the Input-output Model

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Résumé

L'objectif de cette étude est de déterminer l'impact du Covid-19 sur le secteur du tourisme marocain. Pour ce faire nous allons opter pour un modèle Input-Output à l'aide des données du tableau ressource-emploi relatif à l'économie marocaine de 2019, via un choc de la baisse de la consommation des ménages sur la branche H55 (Hôtels et restaurants). Les résultats révèlent qu'après le choc montrent qu'une diminution de la consommation intérieure du tourisme récepteur de 68% a généré une diminution de la valeur ajoutée de 28364,87 en millions Dh. De ce fait une instauration d'un nouveau mécanisme de précaution résistance et de gestion des crises s'impose amplement.

Mots clés : Covid-19, secteur du tourisme, consommation des ménages, modèle Input-Output.

Abstract

The objective of this study is to determine the impact of Covid-19 on the Moroccan tourism sector. To do this we will opt for an Input-Output model using data from the resource-employment table for the Moroccan economy in 2019, via a shock to the decline in household consumption in the H55 (Hotels and Restaurants) branch. The results show that after the shock, a decrease in domestic consumption of inbound tourism of 68% generated a decrease in value added of 28364.87 in million dirham. Therefore, a new mechanism of precautionary resistance and crisis management is essential.

Keywords: Covid-19, tourism sector, household consumption, Input-Output model.

Introduction

Morocco, known as an archipelago, is made famous in the world for its tourism sector. Tourism is one of the most profitable and dynamic economic industries, a useful tool to improve the economic development of any country or territory due to the increase in GDP, and the development of related industries. This driving industry generates economic wealth (it represents a major item in the national gross domestic product, accounting for about 7% of the national GDP in 2019) and contributes to the creation of jobs (an excellent provider of employment with 550,000 direct jobs in 2019, nearly 5% of employment in the entire economy).

The outbreak of a virus in December 2019 disrupted the entire global economic system, and declared in January 2020 as a global pandemic. The pandemic has affected our way of life, such as our right to individual mobility, the measures taken to contain the pandemic resulted in national closures, wide implementation of travel restrictions and border closures, making tourism one of the most affected sectors, however the strict restrictions applied to combat the corona virus pandemic, resulted in a complete halt of the tourism industry. The magnitude of the economic impact of Covid-19 is incomparable to previous crises. According to WTTC (World travel and tourism council) has pointed out that international tourism has shown a 22% decrease in the first quarter of 2020, a percentage that varies however depending on the severity of the infections and the period of the pandemic.

The Covid-19 has certainly had a devastating impact on both the global economy and sectoral economies. The impact can only be analyzed as an external shock, which normally occurs when a negative external shock affects the supply and demand of a product (e.g. hotel services), or the demand and supply of an entire economic sector (e.g. the tourism industry), or the overall economy.

The interest in empirically examining these questions arises with greater importance in the particular context of Morocco, the objective of this study is to characterize, and using data from the resource-employment table relating to the Moroccan economy of 2019, of the High Commission for Planning, to determine the impact of Covid-19 on the Moroccan tourism sector. To do this, we will opt for an Input-Output model via a shock to the decline in household consumption in the H55 branch (Hotels and restaurants).

Therefore, the research question of this study is developed as follows:

Tourism sector in the era of Covid-19: What impact on this industry and what are the macroeconomic aggregates affected in the tourism sector?

The article is structured as follows: In the first part we will present an overview of the theoretical and empirical literature that deals with the impact of the health crisis on tourism. In the second part, we will test our hypotheses through empirical tests following the econometric methodology. Finally, the third part explains the results or effects of the shock simulations on final household consumption in order to draw lessons and recommendations for the conclusion.

1. Literature review

1.1. Theoretical development

Disruptions in the economy, whether military, economic, geographic or health-related, have a direct impact on the entire chain of operations of the tourism industry, and a recession or crisis in the sector could result in the loss of millions of jobs. Nevertheless, the tourism sector is vulnerable to risks such as epidemics, pandemics, catastrophic incidents, terrorism or other activities that jeopardize the safety of travelers (Bassil et al, 2019; Law, 2006).

In this section we have mentioned the theoretical work on the impact of a pandemic on tourism and travel.

Ebola is an infectious disease whose 2014 outbreak negatively impacted the economies of affected countries, primarily West African countries. Among the most affected states are Guinea and Liberia. This epidemic lasted over two years, with much of this damage occurring between July 2014 and May 2015. As with any other contagious disease outbreak, the response has been to avoid traveling to these countries due to fear or advice from governments. A 2018 WTTC report analyzed the effects of Ebola on travel and tourism in affected countries. Guinea recorded a loss of US\$75 million in tourism revenue, a 0.9% decline in its contribution to GDP. MERS originated in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia and caused a short-lived outbreak in 2015, but despite its brevity the resulting impact on the global economy in general was enormous. In South Korea, MERS resulted in the quarantine of 16,000 people, 186 infections and 38 deaths. The outbreak resulted in a 40% drop in international tourists for the first month and 61% for the second month, resulting in a loss of revenue of USD 10.5 billion in the tourism sector (Joo et al; 2019). Similarly the tourism industry in Saudi Arabia has suffered from the epidemic due to travel restrictions. The Saudi Arabian tourism authority reported a loss of revenue of 5 billion USD, Mexico was also affected and lost 3 billion USD in the tourism sector. This was caused by the loss of more than one million tourists and travelers (World Bank; 2017).

The SARS epidemic in 2003 lasted about 7 months and revealed significant effects on economies, despite a relatively small number of cases and deaths. In this pandemic Hon Kong recorded a 68% drop in tourist arrivals, a loss estimated by the WTTC to be \$20 billion in GDP for Singapore, China and Vietnam (McKercher, B. & Chon, K. (2004)). Canada reported 251 cases and 43 deaths, resulting in a loss of \$4.3 billion in the hotel industry and an estimated

5272\$ million in lost food services (Keogh-Brown & Smith, 2008). The World Travel and Tourism Council estimated that up to 3 million people in the industry lost their jobs in the most affected jurisdictions of Hong Kong and Singapore.

1.2 Empirical work

There are many empirical studies on the link between tourism policy and health crisis (Covid-19) in different countries. The interest of these works is to focus on the econometric approaches used which are different from one study to another.

Assion LAWSON SIPOAKA and Mathilde M. ENOUGA (2020) examined the relationship between Covid-19, Tourism and Economic Growth in West Africa Evidence from Senegal and Togo, with a Computable General Equilibrium Model (CGEM) and run respectively two sets of simulations covering a period of seven years (2017 - 2023) for Senegal and nine years for Togo (2015 - 2023). The variables used are: RDIA (the Airport Infrastructure Development Charge) on imported products, the RDIA rate on imports, the world price of the good, the exchange rate and the quantity of the good imported. The RDIA on exported products, rate of RDIA on export, world price, purchase price of the composite product and quantity exported. Their results show that the effect on tourism demand: The decrease of 78% in 2020 and 30% in 2021 of foreign demand induces a decrease in the export demand of tourism services. Effect on value added and GDP: The reduction in VAT on tourism services in Togo has little impact on consumer behavior and therefore on value added. On the other hand, the reduction of the RDIA for the Senegalese economy positively stimulates foreign demand to the point where the variation in the value added of the tourism sector becomes positive again.

Senegal's GDP will shrink by 0.92 percentage points without a stimulus policy and by 0.91 percentage points otherwise. 0.91 percentage points otherwise. In Togo, it would be 1.57 percentage points with or without a stimulus policy. Effect on factor income: The contraction of value added in the market sectors that are relatively more labor-intensive results in a decrease in the demand for labor and therefore a decrease in the wage rate. Effect on labor demand: The decline in foreign demand for tourism services resulting from the Covid-19 would lead to a loss of nearly 9,780 jobs in Senegal compared to 7,936 jobs in Togo. The drop in labor demand in the tourism sector would be 300 for Senegal and 93 for Togo.

Marinko Skare, Domingo Riberio Soriano and Malgorzata Porada-Rocho (2020), seek to assess the impact of COVID-19 on the travel and tourism industry, through Panel Structural Vector Auto regression (PSVAR), for a panel of 185 countries on data from 1995 to 2019. The variables used are: Total (indirect and induced impact) of travel and tourism contribution to national/regional GDP, total (indirect and induced impact) of travel and tourism contribution to national/regional employment, total spending in the national economy by foreign visitors, ARRIVALS = total number of tourist arrivals, PANDEMIC = dichotomous (dummy) variable, PANDEMIC = 1 when there is no pandemic and PANDEMIC = 0 when there is a pandemic. The simulation results indicate that negative shocks will be displayed, not only in the short term but also in the long term, and it will take several years for the travel industry to recover. The travel and tourism industry's contribution to GDP will increase from -\$4.1 trillion to -\$12.8 trillion. As well as the tourism industry's total contribution to employment will fall from -164,506 million to 514,080 million jobs, and the loss of inbound tourism spending will fall by -\$1.9 trillion with capital investment falling from -\$362.9 billion to -\$1.1 trillion. Unlike past pandemic crises.

Loo-See Bech and Woon Leong Lin (2020), analyze the impact of Covid 19 on the ASEAN tourism industry with a VAR panel model using a 12-month period from July 2019 to July 2020, in seven ASEAN countries. The variables used are: the number of confirmed cases, deaths and international tourist arrivals. The method used was set up to account for the bidirectional causality that exists between covid 19 and tourist arrivals. The results revealed that international tourism may be affected by the Covid19 pandemic. Especially for countries considered as tourist destinations such as Malaysia, Thailand and Singapore and for countries with high volume of outbound tourism such as the United States, Europe and China.

2. Methodology of the modeling

2.1. Input-Output model

The classical Input-Output model projects data from an ERR (developed by Leontief in 1941). It is used to study the impact of an increase in final demand or one of its components on the productive system. This model makes it possible to identify the sectors that have the greatest spillover effect on the economy and thus to better target certain public interventions. It also

makes it possible to identify potential bottlenecks that an economy in growth could encounter. The classic analyses of input-output models include only a few behavioral relationships, such as the summary presentation of the production and operating accounts of the sectors, and the supply and use balances of the goods and services available in the economy, without taking into account the accounting operations of the institutional units.

2.2. Field of study

Input-output" models (also called "input-output" models) are the most frequently used tools for estimating the secondary impact of an event. These simulation models make it possible to reconstruct the existing exchanges between the different sectors of an economy. They indicate the extent to which each sector of activity relies on the production of goods and services from other sectors to ensure its production.

Indeed, the method that measures the magnitude between covid-19 and the tourism sector is the input-output model. This approach will make it possible to determine the sectors that will be structurally affected by a shock to the tourism sector.

Based on the ERR 2019 which is the latest table (input - output) of the national accounts available at the HCP website. As well as it is assumed that the Covid-19 was in 2019. To determine the impact of the health crisis on the tourism sector represented by the branch H55 (Hotels and restaurants). It should also be mentioned that this branch cannot be disaggregated because most hotels have a restaurant, which is why the national accounts take the branch as a whole.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Results

Relationship between the tourism sector and the other sectors of the economy: analysis of technical coefficients.

Focusing on the results of the technical coefficients of the branch " hotels and restaurants ", we notice that to satisfy a final demand of 1 DH of tourist product, it is necessary to produce 0.0429 of Agriculture, forest and annexed services, 0.0092 of Fishing, aquaculture, 0.0001 of the

Extraction industry, 0.1770 of the Food and tobacco industries, 0.0017 of the Textile and leather industries, 0.0058 of the Chemical and Para-chemical industries, 0.0037 of the Mechanical, metallurgical and electrical industries, 0.0080 of the Other manufacturing industries except oil refining, 0.0078 of Petroleum refining and other energy products, 0.0199 of Electricity and water, 0.0006 of Construction and public works, 0.0001 of Trade, 0.0055 of Hotels and restaurants (intra consumption), 0.0210 of Financial activities and insurance ...Generally, the coefficients closest to satisfy the final demand of the branch "Hotels and restaurants" are: Food industries and tobacco, Agriculture, forestry and related services, Financial activities and insurance, Real estate, renting and business services, Financial activities and insurance, Electricity and water and Fishing, aquaculture.

3.2. Result of the shock

The input-output analysis developed by Leontief (1936, 1941) makes it possible to predict the influence of exogenous supply or demand shocks on the economy as a whole.

The crucial step in our study is to shock the H55 branch to observe the effect of Covid-19 on this branch. Our shock value is determined by a drop in domestic consumption of inbound tourism of 68%. For this we consider that all the branches are exogenous except for the "Hotels and restaurants" branch which is the subject of our simulation.

These results are obtained with the help of automated calculations made on the Excel table.

While the negative shock on the final consumption of households has had a negative impact on the branch "hotels and restaurants" namely -2.50 points.

3.3. Discussion

The advent of Covid-19 in Morocco, evokes a negative influence on tourism, the sector is in total stop of activity since mid-March until May. On the other hand, the activities related to tourism (accommodation, catering, crafts, events ...) have suffered the full force of the effects of containment and closure of borders. Namely, a downward trend in air traffic during the year 2020 of 71.48% compared to the same period of the year 2019, welcoming 7150277 passengers against 25075095 passengers in 2019. The turnover of the handicraft companies would have decreased by about 71% at the end of May 2020, and a loss of employment of 37000 in the

handicraft activities. The number of tourist arrivals fell by 79% (MRE -77%, TES -80%) to reach 2.8 million arrivals and that of tourist nights by 72% to reach 6.97 million nights with -80% for foreigners and -55% for nationals. As well as a loss of 82,000 jobs, 47% of which are in accommodation and catering, i.e. 3,540 jobs, 22% in transport, i.e. 1,840 jobs and 31% in other tourist activities (tourist guides, etc.), i.e. a loss of 2,520 jobs. While travel receipts are down 54% in 2020, after an increase of 7.8% a year earlier, a loss of 42.4 billion dirham.

The sectors of the Moroccan economy are almost affected by the pandemic to different degrees, including the tourism industry; the production of the branch, intermediate consumption and value added tend to a decreasing curve by showing respectively 43683.29; 15318.4161; 28364.87 in million dirham. This fall is strongly explained by the closure of the borders within the framework of the restrictions of the fight against the pandemic.

While the total production of the branches has experienced a decline of 2.50%, its weight has collapsed the intermediate consumption of the branches resulting a percentage of 2.01%. Finally, the value added shows a decrease of 2.82%.

Conclusion

We have attempted to assess the impact of Covid-19 on the tourism sector through the decline in domestic consumption of inbound tourism, using the input output model. This model also clarified the role of inbound tourism in either pursuing an austerity or a recovery policy for the tourism sector in Morocco.

The results reveal that after the shock of the final consumption of the households, we obtain a decrease of the branch H55 2.50 points. This explains why domestic tourism is a crucial element in this industry. The value added of this branch fell by 28364.87 million Dh. However, the value added of all branches has varied by 2.82%.

Thierry Breton, European Commissioner for the Internal Market "there is an opportunity to take advantage of the current crisis to reinvent the tourism of tomorrow towards a more sustainable, resilient and innovative sector. At this level, decision makers and practitioners in the tourism industry need to develop a new crisis preparedness mechanism to combat the current and future pandemic crises. To do so, they need to gain empirical knowledge about the true nature and extent of the Covid-19 crisis.

Today the new development model is ideal for reviving tourism through strengthening the sustainability of the sector and adapting to the new mode of marketing with the digital transformation of the sector and its vertical, horizontal and territorial integration.

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